

Scalable Virtual Lab for Remote Experiments on AI-powered Edge Devices

1st Baptiste Dupertuis
Embedded Computing Systems
HE-Arc / HES-SO
Neuchâtel, Switzerland
baptiste.dupertuis@he-arc.ch

2nd Maïck Huguenin
Embedded Computing Systems
HE-Arc / HES-SO
Neuchâtel, Switzerland
maick.huguenin@he-arc.ch

3rd Margaux Divernois and Gregoire Rebstein
Interaction Technologies
HE-Arc / HES-SO
Neuchâtel, Switzerland
margaux.divernois@he-arc.ch

5th Maria Buckley, Iain Keaney
and Léonie Buckley
Ubotica Technologies
Dublin, Ireland
maria.buckley@ubotica.com

6th Nuria Pazos
Embedded Computing Systems
HE-Arc / HES-SO
Neuchâtel, Switzerland
nuria.pazosescudero@he-arc.ch

Abstract—Developing edge AI for industrial applications presents two main challenges: (1) achieving consistent result reproducibility across diverse edge devices and (2) managing the complexities of configuring heterogeneous platforms, which can significantly extend evaluation times. Consequently, running experiments and comparing results across various embedded boards becomes more challenging, particularly when working with devices from multiple manufacturers.

This work introduces a scalable virtual laboratory, dAIEdge-VLab, for running remote experiments on AI-powered edge devices. dAIEdge-VLab is tailored for users without embedded programming expertise or direct access to specific hardware, allowing them to perform real-time AI experiments on a remote collection of embedded boards. The platform supports a range of experiments, including AI model benchmarking, AI application benchmarking, hardware-in-the-loop neural architecture search (NAS), and on-device training benchmarks.

The dAIEdge-VLab architecture aims to connect data scientists with embedded systems, providing a scalable, vendor-neutral platform for effortless running of AI experiments on actual edge hardware. The proposed platform features a modular architecture that allows for easy integration of remote embedded boards. The outcomes of integrating a third-party AI-powered edge device for AI model benchmarking are presented.

Index Terms—Edge@AI, Edge Computing, Virtual Lab., AI-powered Edge Devices, Machine Learning

I. INTRODUCTION

EDGE AI processes data directly on embedded boards located at the network’s edge, close to where data is generated. This setup reduces latency, enabling faster, real-time responses. By eliminating the need to transmit data to the cloud, edge AI also enhances privacy and security while reducing bandwidth requirements. Although edge devices typically have less computational power than cloud-based solutions,

This work has been funded by the European Network of Excellence dAIEdge under Grant Agreement No. 101120726. The associated partners from Switzerland received funding from the Swiss State Secretariat for Education, Research and Innovation (SERI)

recent hardware advancements have greatly improved their capacity to manage complex AI tasks.

Today, many cloud-based AI development services enable software developers, including those without data science expertise, to leverage AI models via APIs, SDKs, or applications. However, few of these services support edge deployment, which demands specialized skills in embedded programming and system integration to effectively optimize and deploy AI models on specific edge devices. The complexity of comparing AI experiments results across different embedded boards grows further when targeting devices from multiple vendors.

We believe that a unified Edge AI service with remote access to multiple AI-powered edge devices (including MPUs¹, GPGPUs², MCUs³, NPUs⁴, and VPUs⁵) is essential for fair comparisons of AI experiments across hardware types. An online platform would effectively meet this need, enabling consistent and equitable evaluation across different edge devices.

A. Novelty Aspect

To the best of our knowledge, there is currently no vendor-neutral, multi-platform, scalable solution for running AI experiments on a remote board farm. This work fills that gap by presenting a flexible, vendor-independent, and scalable virtual lab that enables edge AI experiments, helping to bridge the gap between data scientists and the embedded systems field.

B. Structure of the Paper

The structure of the paper is as follows: Section II provides a comparison of the dAIEdge-VLab solution with current state-of-the-art methods for remotely executing AI experiments on

¹Micro Processor Units

²General-Purpose Graphics Processing Units

³Micro Controllers Units

⁴Neural Processing Units

⁵Vision Processing Units

board farms. Section III describes the scalable architecture of dAIEdge-VLab, focusing on its capacity to integrate third-party embedded boards seamlessly. Section IV discusses the implementation details of dAIEdge-VLab, while Section V presents results from integrating the Myriad X processor into the platform. Lastly, Section VI concludes the paper and outlines directions for future research.

II. STATE-OF-THE-ART

In the literature we find various publications dedicated to developing methodologies for fair comparisons of hardware, algorithms, and optimization techniques within the Edge AI space. Among these, QuTiBench [1] presents an innovative multi-tier benchmarking framework that integrates algorithmic optimizations, such as quantization, to assist system developers in evaluating the capabilities and limitations of new compute architectures for specific neural networks. The QuTiBench team has encouraged contributions from the community to cover a comprehensive range of Machine Learning system implementations; however, contributions stopped in 2021, and the project now appears inactive. Subsequent studies, such as [2], have adopted a similar framework for assessing Machine Learning inference on edge computing platforms. This benchmarking environment currently includes two hardware compute engines—the CPU-based Raspberry Pi 4 and the Google Edge TPU accelerator—alongside two inference frameworks: TensorFlow-Lite and Arm NN.

Recently, several edge device providers, including STM, Intel, and Qualcomm, have introduced their first online remote benchmarking solutions. STM offers the STM32Cube.AI Developer Cloud [3], a free platform that supports developers in creating, optimizing, benchmarking, and deploying AI solutions specifically for STM32 microcontrollers and microprocessors based on ARM Cortex processors. This platform also supports AI hardware acceleration (NPU) where available on the target device. Similarly, Intel has launched the Intel Tiber Developer Cloud [4], providing developers unrestricted access to Intel’s latest edge computing hardware and software platforms. Finally, Qualcomm AI Hub [5] allows remote users to run profiling jobs that measure the resources required to run optimized models across various Qualcomm devices. The collected metrics help users determine if a model fits within specific time and memory budgets.

Additionally, vendor-neutral commercial solutions have begun to emerge, such as the Impulse Embedded Remote Benchmarking Service [8]. This platform allows developers to remotely test AI models across a broad spectrum of GPU hardware, ranging from entry-level devices like the Jetson Nano to high-performance systems like the AGX Orin. As we understand it, only GPGPU devices are currently accessible for remote benchmarking.

We believe that achieving fair comparisons across various AI-powered edge devices—including MPUs, GPGPUs, MCUs, NPUs, and VPUs—requires a unified service with remote access to a diverse selection of embedded boards. An

Fig. 1. Layer Concept of dAIEdge-VLab

online platform would significantly address this need, allowing for consistent and equitable evaluations across different hardware types. Additionally, the platform should be modular and scalable, allowing for seamless integration of third-party boards.

III. SCALABLE DAIEDGE-VLAB ARCHITECTURE

The proposed scalable virtual lab for running AI experiments on AI-powered edge devices follows a modular concept made up of 5 main layers as depicted in Fig. 1.

1) User Interface (UI) Layer

- **Web Interface/Dashboard:** The virtual lab includes an intuitive web-based dashboard that enables data scientists and developers to interact with the system. Through this interface, users can upload AI models, select target hardware, set up benchmarking parameters, and monitor results.
- **CLI API:** An API-based interface allows easy integration with custom AI pipelines for seamless workflow automation.
- **AI Application Management:** Users can upload pre-trained models, select from a model library, or choose a full AI application including pre- and post-processing. The system also supports model versioning for easy retrieval and comparison of different versions.

2) Orchestration Layer

- **Resource Management and Scheduling:** This component orchestrates resources across multiple platforms, ensuring efficient hardware allocation for testing and benchmarking. It manages job queues, schedules tasks, and optimizes resource use based on platform availability.
- **Virtualization and Containerization:** Models and benchmarking tasks are containerized (e.g., via Docker) to ensure compatibility across diverse hardware, enabling deployment on various edge devices regardless of OS or architecture. This layer manages containers on devices with general-purpose operating systems.

- **Benchmark Configuration:** Users define test cases by specifying hardware configurations, datasets, and performance metrics like latency, power consumption, and accuracy. This configuration standardizes benchmarking for effective comparison across setups.

3) Edge Device Layer (Embedded boards)

- **Multi-Platform Hardware Pool:** The system integrates a range of edge devices, from low-power IoT platforms (e.g., STM32 MCUs, RISC-V boards) to high-performance systems (e.g., Raspberry Pi, Jetson Orin Nano, AGX). This variety supports comprehensive testing across different edge environments.
- **Remote Access and Control:** Users have remote access to actual physical hardware, allowing them to deploy AI models and AI applications on real devices for testing under realistic conditions, without the constraints of simulated environments.

4) Data and Model Processing Layer

- **Data Preprocessing and Inference:** This layer handles data preprocessing and manages inference execution on edge devices, adapting models to meet target hardware limitations like memory and processing power.
- **Performance Metrics Collection:** During benchmarking, this layer monitors key performance metrics—such as inference time, throughput, power consumption, and memory usage—and feeds this data back into the system for analysis by the user.

5) Analytics and Reporting Layer

- **Results Analysis and Visualization:** Benchmarking results are processed and displayed through interactive dashboards, enabling users to compare metrics across hardware platforms. Comprehensive reports offer insights into factors like energy efficiency, processing latency, accuracy, and other performance metrics.

The modular architecture of the dAIEdge-VLab allows for easy integration of remote embedded boards. Fig. 2 depicts the overall architecture of the distributed dAIEdge-VLab. The key elements of this architecture are the following:

- **Remote user:** A user willing to run an AI experiment on a Remote node submits their request via a web-based interface. For direct interaction through the VLab API, the user needs a lightweight local installation.
- **Peer-to-Peer Content Delivery Network:** This open system facilitates data exchange between remote users and remote nodes without relying on a centralized server, enabling fully decentralized communication.
- **Remote host:** Located at the Remote Nnode owner’s site, the Remote host handles node-specific tasks such as running scripts, compiling and deploying the AI model or AI application to the Remote node, collecting benchmarking

Fig. 2. Distributed Architecture of dAIEdge-VLab

results, and sending them back to the user via the peer-to-peer content delivery network.

- **Remote node:** The embedded board where AI experiments are performed. A single Remote host can manage multiple Remote nodes within the owner’s location.

IV. DAIEDGE-VLAB IMPLEMENTATION

An initial implementation of the dAIEdge-VLab, which includes AI model benchmarking experiments on supported AI-powered edge devices, has been completed. The process that dAIEdge-VLab follows to initiate a benchmarking experiment is outlined below:

- 1) **User Interface layer:** A Remote User submits a benchmarking request via the web interface, specifying the trained model, target Remote node, and Machine Learning Runtime (MLR) to be used from the available options.
- 2) **Orchestration layer:** A dAIEdge-VLab API on the Remote User side is responsible for requesting access to the target Remote node to run the benchmarking experiment. Once access is granted based on node availability, a peer-to-peer content delivery network transmits the request to the selected board via the associated Remote host.
- 3) **Data and Model Processing layer:** The Remote host executes the node-specific scripts (*AI_Support*, *AI_Build*, *AI_Deploy*, *AI_Manager* - see below) using the tools within the Docker container, producing a binary tailored for the target Remote node. This binary is then deployed onto the Remote node.
- 4) **Edge Device layer:** Runs the inference/benchmarking process and sends back the collected benchmarking metrics to the Remote host.
- 5) **Analytics and Reporting layer:** The Remote host retrieves the benchmarking metrics from the Remote Node and returns them to the Remote user for visualization through the web interface.

To manage input data preprocessing and inference execution on the target edge device, a structured approach is required for

implementing node-specific scripts within the Data and Model Processing layer. This setup includes four primary scripts and a Docker image that contains all necessary tools and packages for the specific node. These components are organized as follows:

- 1) *AI_Support*:
 - Provides documentation, dependencies, and installation support for the Remote node. For edge devices with OS support, an OS kernel binary image along with system libraries will be provided for flashing onto the target board.
 - Includes scripts to initiate code generation for the benchmarking application specific to the Remote node, which will be saved in the *AI_Project* folder.
- 2) *AI_Project*:
 - Stores the generated benchmarking application that is optimized for execution on the Remote node.
- 3) *AI_Build*:
 - Contains the build environment with toolchains required by the inference framework to cross-compile the benchmarking application.
 - Provides scripts for cross compiling the benchmarking application on the Remote host.
- 4) *AI_Deploy*:
 - Includes tools for deploying the generated binary file onto the Remote node.
 - Provides scripts to automate the deployment of the binary for the benchmarking application onto the Remote node.
- 5) *AI_Manager*:
 - A management tool integrated with the inference framework to control the target board and monitor the system's status.
 - Includes scripts to establish a connection with the Remote node and retrieve benchmarking metrics.

This structure ensures the smooth execution of remote benchmarking tasks across different edge devices, while maintaining consistency in deployment and management. Additionally, Remote node owners who wish to add their boards to the dAIEdge-VLab can find the integration guidelines under [6]. To streamline the process, templates for MPU/Linux and MCU/RTOS are available, facilitating the quick integration of new Remote nodes.

The current implementation of dAIEdge-VLab supports a broad range of Linux-based MPUs, including the Raspberry Pi 4B and Raspberry Pi 5, as well as GPGPUs such as the Nvidia Jetson Xavier and Jetson Orin Nano. It also supports MCU+NPU platforms like the STM32MP257, in addition to bare-metal MCUs such as the STM32L4R9 and NXP LPC55S69. Furthermore, VLab supports vendor-agnostic Machine Learning runtimes like ONNX Runtime, TensorFlow Lite, and TensorFlow Lite for microcontrollers, alongside vendor-specific runtimes such as CUBE-AI and TensorRT.

V. RESULTS - INTEGRATION OF MYRIAD X TO DAIEDGE-VLAB

Recently, Ubotica has enhanced the capabilities of the dAIEdge-VLab by introducing support to the Myriad X processor through the Rupia benchmarking tool.

The Myriad X is a VPU with a Neural Compute Engine developed by Intel Movidius. The Myriad X is designed for on-device NN⁶s and computer vision applications [7], and the custom vector processors within it provide high-performance parallel and hardware accelerated compute within a low power envelope.

In order to run a network on a Myriad device, a Myriad-specific version must be compiled using Intel's OpenVINO toolkit [8]. The OpenVINO toolkit libraries are over 290Mb in size, making for a long installation process. The dAIEdge-VLab architecture, where remote hosts are deployed within docker containers, mitigates this installation process, as the OpenVINO toolkit libraries are pre-installed on the Docker image. Compilation to the Myriad X is a two step process, optimization and compilation, and is shown in Fig. 3. Both optimization and compilation are performed within the *AI_Build* scripts.

Fig. 3. Complete conversion flow of OpenVINO toolchain

Inference is performed on the Myriad X using the Rupia application. Rupia allows users to remotely deploy NNs to Myriad devices. The Rupia client application generates a https request containing the user's compiled model, input tensors and inference specifications. The request is sent to the Rupia backend, hosted on a Ubotica internal server. The backend architecture, depicted in Fig. 4, combines a MongoDB database for data management and RabbitMQ for request queue maintenance, with additional containerization used to ensure security between requests. The Myriad X is referred to as "Cognisat_Mx" in the diagram. The Rupia request is made within the *AI_Deploy* scripts which will wait until the results are downloaded after inference.

The *AI_Manager* script in the Myriad X host handles extracting inference metrics from the results returned by the Rupia client application. The results page of Myriad X benchmarking is shown in Fig. 5.

⁶Neural Networks

Fig. 4. Rupia architecture diagram

The current integration of the Myriad X benchmarking on the dAIEdge-VLab supports NNs in ONNX format only. Additional expansion is planned to increase the metrics collected and reported by Rupia during inference.

Fig. 5. Myriad X dAIEdge-VLab Benchmarking Results

VI. CONCLUSION

Evaluating machine learning (ML) inference on edge devices is a crucial step in choosing the most suitable embedded board or fine-tuning the ML model for specific hardware. However, gaining access to boards from different manufacturers and learning their unique programming environments can be complex and challenging. To overcome these barriers and facilitate access to a wide variety of embedded boards, this paper proposes a solution for conducting AI experiments on remote AI-powered embedded boards.

The current dAIEdge-VLab implementation supports a broad range of Linux-based MPUs, including the Raspberry Pi 4B and Raspberry Pi 5, as well as GPGPUs like the Nvidia Jetson Xavier and Nvidia Jetson Orin Nano. It also integrates MCU+NPU platforms such as the STM32MP257, alongside bare-metal MCUs like the STM32L4R9 and NXP LPC55S69. Furthermore, it includes support for both vendor-agnostic ML runtimes, such as ONNX Runtime, TensorFlow Lite, and TensorFlow Lite for Microcontrollers, and vendor-specific ML runtimes, including CUBE-AI and TensorRT. Designed to be scalable, dAIEdge-VLab enables seamless integration of third-party embedded boards in a distributed setup. Ubotica has recently expanded dAIEdge-VLab’s capabilities by adding support for the Myriad X processor via the Rupia benchmarking tool.

dAIEdge-VLab currently provides support for users lacking expertise in embedded programming or direct access to specific embedded boards by enabling real-time model benchmarking on remote hardware. Looking ahead, the platform will expand to include additional experiments, such as benchmarking AI applications, enabling hardware-in-the-loop neural architecture search (NAS), and offering on-device training directly on the target board.

In the near future, we plan to enhance the distributed version of dAIEdge-VLab by integrating blockchain technology, enabling decentralized sharing and management of information about registered embedded boards.

REFERENCES

- [1] M. Blott, L. Halder, M. Leeser, and L. Doyle, “Qutibench: Benchmarking neural networks on heterogeneous hardware,” *J. Emerg. Technol. Comput. Syst.*, vol. 15, no. 4, Dec. 2019. [Online]. Available: <https://doi.org/10.1145/3358700>
- [2] P. Amanatidis, G. Iosifidis, and D. Karampatzakis, “Comparative evaluation of machine learning inference machines on edge-class devices,” in *Proceedings of the 25th Pan-Hellenic Conference on Informatics*, ser. PCI ’21. New York, NY, USA: Association for Computing Machinery, 2022, p. 102–106. [Online]. Available: <https://doi.org/10.1145/3503823.3503843>
- [3] STM32 AI Solutions, “Stm32cube.ai developer cloud.” [Online]. Available: <https://www.st.com/en/development-tools/stm32cubeai-dc.html>
- [4] Intel AI Cloud, “Intel tiber ai cloud.” [Online]. Available: <https://www.intel.com/content/www/us/en/developer/tools/devcloud/services.html>
- [5] Qualcomm AI, “Qualcom ai hub: The platform form on-device ai.” [Online]. Available: <https://aihub.qualcomm.com/>
- [6] B. Dupertuis, “daiedge-vlab documentation.” [Online]. Available: <http://public-virtuallab-docs-tica-23tica04-daiedge-poc-6eb4f1c0e44fb2.pages-rad.ing.he-arc.ch/docs/>
- [7] Intel Corporation, “Intel movidius myriad x vpu product brief.” [Online]. Available: <https://www.intel.com/content/www/us/en/products/docs/processors/movidius-vpu/myriad-x-product-brief.html>
- [8] —, “Openvino documentation.” [Online]. Available: https://docs.openvino.ai/2022.3/openvino_ocs_model_optimization_guide.html